

The Influence of Personal Ethics on Financial Reporting Quality

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between personal ethics and financial reporting quality among accounting professionals at the University of Benin using a descriptive survey research design. The population comprised 120 professionals, including accountants, auditors, financial controllers, budget officers, and accounting academics. A sample size of 92 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane's formula, and a stratified random sampling technique ensured proportional representation across professional groups. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaire, whose validity and reliability were confirmed through expert review and pilot testing. Data analysis was carried out using multiple regression techniques to evaluate the influence of integrity, professional competence, accountability, and self-discipline on financial reporting quality. The findings reveal that all four ethical dimensions have positive and statistically significant effects on financial reporting quality. Integrity emerged as the strongest predictor, followed by professional competence, accountability, and self-discipline. The overall regression model was also statistically significant. The study concludes that ethical attributes significantly enhance the accuracy, transparency, and reliability of financial reports. It emphasizes that beyond technical compliance with accounting standards, ethical orientation plays a crucial role in ensuring credible financial reporting. The study recommends strengthening ethics training, promoting continuous professional development, accountability, and self-discipline among financial professionals to improve reporting quality.

Keywords: Integrity, Accountability, Professional competence, Reporting quality

JEL Classifications: G40, G41

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1. Introduction

Financial reporting is essential in providing stakeholders with accurate and timely information. Its core objective is to present a true and fair view of an organisation's financial position and performance (IFAC, 2020). Personal ethical qualities such as professional competence, integrity, and accountability are increasingly acknowledged as key determinants of reporting quality. Empirical studies indicate that these attributes mitigate fraudulent behaviour, promote transparency (Barth et al., 2008), and reduce earnings management practices (Graham et al., 2017), especially in contexts where regulatory frameworks are weak or ineffective. While ethical frameworks guide behaviour, individual moral judgment ultimately drives decisions in discretionary areas such as revenue recognition (Nelson, 2003). This creates an "ethical gap," especially where oversight is limited (Okike, 2007). Major scandals like Enron, WorldCom, Wirecard and Cadbury in Nigeria illustrate how ethical failures erode trust and enable fraud. Psychological research (Murphy & Dacin, 2011, Omoye & Wilson-Oshilim, 2025) shows that even well-intentioned individuals may rationalize unethical actions, highlighting the limits of governance systems alone.

This study therefore examines how personal ethics influence financial reporting quality. Reporting failures persist against IFRS, FASB frameworks and standards, and IESBA guidelines. These standards promote consistency and transparency, yet cannot fully address ethical behaviour. Violations often stem from individual failings; lack of integrity, accountability, or competence. Professionals under pressure may manipulate earnings or misrepresent performance to meet expectations or secure incentives (Dichev et al., 2013). Such practices damage credibility, cause financial losses, and undermine trust. The persistence of misconduct reveals a gap between ethical instruction and practice. While ethics education is emphasized, professionals often face pressures or ambiguous situations where rules provide limited guidance. In such cases, personal values become decisive. While extant literature has predominantly focused on either institutional determinants or individual ethical attributes as separate explanations of reporting quality, relatively few studies have examined their combined influence.

Moreover, the University of Benin has received limited scholarly attention in this regard, notwithstanding its significance as a major public higher education institution operating

within a resource-constrained and accountability-driven environment. Consequently, this study contributes to the literature by investigating the interplay between personal ethics and organisational pressures in shaping reporting outcomes within the University of Benin context.

1.1. Objectives of the study

- i. To assess the extent to which integrity influences the accuracy and reliability of financial reporting quality.
- ii. To examine the effect of professional competence on the transparency of financial reporting practices.
- iii. To investigate the relationship between accountability and compliance with established accounting standards.
- iv. To determine how self-discipline affects the prevention of unethical manipulations in financial statements.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual framework

2.1.1. Personal ethics

These are values, principles, and beliefs that guide an individual's behaviour and decisions in both personal and professional contexts. These ethical attributes are internally developed and shaped by cultural, religious, educational, and social experiences, and they serve as a moral compass in everyday judgment and professional duties. In the accounting and financial reporting context, personal ethics are critical, as they influence how individuals interpret and apply accounting standards, especially in situations involving ambiguity or discretion. Personal ethics significantly impact ethical reasoning and behaviour in accounting practices. They posit that individual ethical orientation plays a decisive role in determining the honesty and transparency of financial disclosures. Personal ethics are fundamental to ethical sensitivity and decision-making in accounting.

Professional Competence

Professional competence in accounting is the ability to perform one's professional duties to a defined standard, encompassing technical knowledge, professional skills, ethical values, and attitudes to serve the public interest. Professional competence encompasses

cognitive, technical, integrative, contextual, relational, affective/moral dimensions, and habits of mind; it is developmental, impermanent, and context-dependent (Epstein & Hundert, 2002).

Transparency

Transparency suggests the extent to which an organisation provides stakeholders with clear, accurate, complete, and timely financial information regarding its activities and financial position. It is a fundamental principle of financial reporting that promotes openness in the disclosure of relevant information, thereby enabling users of financial statements to make informed economic decisions. Transparency reduces information asymmetry between management and stakeholders by ensuring that material financial events, transactions, and risks are adequately communicated (Bushman et al., 2004). It also strengthens accountability by allowing stakeholders to assess whether resources are being managed efficiently and in accordance with established regulations and ethical standards. In practice, transparency is reflected in the quality and comprehensiveness of disclosures relating to contingent liabilities, related-party transactions, risk exposures, and other material financial matters. High levels of transparency enhance stakeholder confidence, improve corporate governance, and contribute to the credibility and reliability of financial reports (Barth et al., 2008; Healy & Palepu, 2001).

Accountability

Accountability refers to the obligation of an individual or organization is responsible for explaining and justifying its actions and decisions, particularly in relation to financial matters and the use of entrusted resources. Accountability is often regarded as an elusive and multidimensional concept because its meaning varies across contexts and relationships. According to Amanda Sinclair (1995), accountability is fundamentally a social relationship in which individuals or organisations are required to explain and justify their actions to others who have the authority to evaluate and sanction those actions. In financial reporting, accountability implies that managers and public officials are responsible for the stewardship of resources entrusted to them and must provide accurate, reliable, and transparent information regarding their use of those resources (Sinclair, 1995).

Self-discipline

Self-discipline is the ability to control your own actions and make sure you follow through with your decisions. It was also defined as the ability to suppress powerful responses in the pursuit of a higher objective, which is not automatic but involves conscious effort (Duckworth & Seligman, 2006).

2.1.3. Financial reporting quality (FRQ)

Financial Reporting Quality is the degree to which financial statements provide a true and fair view of an entity's financial position, performance, and cash flows. High-quality financial reporting ensures that the information presented is faithfully represented, relevant, verifiable, comparable, and timely, as outlined by the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC, 2020). In order to better analyse the entity's operations. FRQ takes into account the completeness of the reported information. Information about an entity's cash flow is of great interest to investors. According to IASB (2008), financial reporting is an essential accounting practice that tends to provide information users with the necessary data for economic decision-making about the evaluation of an entity's performance and profitability. In order to improve the quality of financial reporting, other mechanism such as the use of both personal ethics and artificial intelligence has been employed (Wilson-Oshilim & Efedhoma, 2024). Barth *et al.* (2008) stress the importance of conservatism, the asymmetric verification criterion that demands greater certainty for identifying gains than losses. Thus, FRQ is not merely a technical construct but one deeply intertwined with ethical behaviour.

2.2. Theoretical review

Kohlberg's Theory of Moral Development provides a useful framework for understanding the relationship between personal ethics and financial reporting quality in this study. According to Kohlberg (1981), moral reasoning develops through three levels; pre-conventional, conventional, and post-conventional with higher stages characterised by adherence to ethical principles rather than personal interests or external pressures. The personal ethics variables examined in this study, professional competence, integrity, accountability, and self-discipline—are closely linked to moral development. Professional competence reflects a commitment to applying professional standards and responsibilities effectively, while integrity involves honesty and consistency in ethical decision-making.

Accountability demonstrates a willingness to accept responsibility for actions and provide transparent justifications for decisions, whereas self-discipline enables individuals to resist unethical behaviour and adhere to established regulations and professional codes. The study's findings, particularly the significant influence of integrity and accountability on financial reporting quality, are consistent with Kohlberg's post-conventional stage, where individuals act according to universal ethical principles such as fairness, transparency, and justice. Professionals operating at this level are more likely to produce accurate, reliable, and transparent financial reports, even when faced with organisational pressures. Conversely, individuals at lower stages of moral reasoning may prioritise personal or institutional interests, increasing the risk of unethical reporting practices.

2.3. Empirical review

It is often acknowledged that integrity is an essential quality in the creation and display of superior financial reports. Financial professionals are guided by these personal principles to uphold honesty, refrain from deceit, and guarantee the accuracy of financial data provided to stakeholders. People are less prone to alter statistics for their own or their organization's benefit when they maintain integrity. Integrity also means continuously adhering to moral and ethical standards, even when there is no oversight or outside enforcement. Fehmi and Ibrahim (2021) examined the interaction between ethical climate and individual ethics in influencing financial reporting outcomes using a survey research design. Their findings revealed that personal ethical values significantly shape ethical behaviour and reporting practices, reinforcing the importance of individual integrity in financial reporting. Integrity, defined as steadfast adherence to ethical principles, promotes consistency in decision-making, particularly under pressure (Carter, 1996; Verschoor, 2006).

Kaplan (2001), through an experimental study involving accounting professionals, found that ethical decision-making is strongly influenced by honesty when individuals face conflicting interests. Similarly, Bailey et al. (2010), using behavioural research methods, reported that integrity serves as a mediating factor in resisting unethical instructions from superiors. In Nigeria, Akintola Okike (2007), through a review of corporate reporting practices, found that professionals with strong ethical values were less likely to succumb to pressures for fraudulent reporting.

Ethical reasoning has also been identified as a critical determinant of transparent reporting. Drawing on cognitive moral development theory, James Rest (1986) and Linda Treviño (1986) argued that ethical reasoning enables professionals to distinguish right from wrong in complex situations. Using survey-based data from accounting practitioners, Sweeney et al. (2010) found that stronger ethical reasoning increased the likelihood of truthful disclosure of sensitive financial information. Likewise, Mayhew and Murphy (2009), employing an experimental design with accounting students, demonstrated that ethics education significantly enhances ethical reasoning and reporting decisions. Similarly, Libby and Thorne (2007) developed a conceptual framework linking auditors' ethical virtues, including honesty and courage, to improved transparency and disclosure quality. Accountability has also been associated with improved reporting quality.

Osemeke and Adegbite (2016) employed a mixed-method approach involving surveys, interviews, documentary analysis, and focus groups to examine corporate governance practices in Nigeria. Their findings indicated that leadership commitment, ethical culture, and accountability mechanisms enhance compliance with governance standards and reporting requirements. Ben Agyei-Mensah (2017) analysed 174 firm-year observations from listed firms in Ghana and Botswana using content analysis and regression techniques and found that stronger governance accountability mechanisms were associated with higher compliance with IFRS disclosure requirements. These findings suggest that accountability, ethical reasoning, and integrity collectively contribute to greater transparency, reliability, and quality in financial reporting.

3. Methodology

This study uses a descriptive survey research approach to investigate the relationship between personal ethics and financial reporting quality among professionals at the University of Benin. The population comprises of accounting professionals at the University of Benin, categorised into four strata based on their roles: Accountants, Auditors, Financial Directors, Budget Officers, and Accounting academics. These groups were chosen because they have direct experience with financial reporting and ethical decision-making. The entire accessible population in the university system were 120 related professionals. To determine the sample size, Taro Yamane's formula (1967) was employed and this gave rise to the sample size of 92.

A stratified random sampling technique is used to ensure that each professional category is represented proportionally. The stratified random sampling method ensured proportional representation across strata. This study relied solely on primary data to get first-hand information from respondents at the University of Benin. Questionnaire was distributed in person, and via email to the University's accounting, finance, and audit staff. To verify validity, academic supervisors and accounting and ethics specialists examined the draft questionnaire, and dependability was tested in a pilot study. Cronbach's alpha was used to examine the instrument's internal consistency, with a 0.70 level regarded satisfactory (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

To empirically analyse the influence of personal ethics on financial reporting quality, a multiple regression model was specified:

$$FRQ = \beta_0 + \beta_1INT + \beta_2PC + \beta_3ACC + \beta_4SD + \varepsilon \dots (1)$$

Where: INT=Interest; PC=Professional competence; ACC= Accountability; SD=Self Discipline. β_0 = Constant / Intercept. β_1 - β_4 represents the coefficients of the independent variables. ε = Error term indicating unexplained variation.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Results

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the 92 respondents who participated in the study. The gender distribution shows the gender distribution of respondents, with 63 males (68.5%) and 29 females (31.5%), making a total of 92 respondents (100%). This indicates that the sample is male-dominated, as men constitute more than twice the number of women. In terms of age, majority of the respondents, 68.5% (63), are below 30 years, while 18.5% (17) fall within the 30–39 years range. Those aged 40–49 years constitute 10.9% (10), and only 2.2% (2) are 50 years and above. This indicates that the study population is predominantly youthful, with fewer middle-aged and older participants. The professional role of the respondents reveals that accounting academics represent the largest group with 42.4% (39), followed by accountants at 23.9% (22). Auditors make up 17.4% (16), while financial controllers and budget officers account for 16.3% (15). This suggests that the study sample is diverse, but is dominated by participants from the academic accounting field.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	63	68.5%
	Female	29	31.5%
	Total	92	100%
Age	Below 30	63	68.5%
	30-39	17	18.5%
	40-49	10	10.9%
	50 years and above	2	2.2%
	Total	92	100%
Professional Role	Accountant	22	23.9%
	Auditor	16	17.4%
	Financial Controllers and Budget Officers	15	16.3%
	Accounting Academic	39	42.4%
	Total	92	100%
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	68	73.9%
	5-10 years	19	20.7%
	More than 10 years	5	5.4%
	Total	92	100%
Highest Educational Qualification	B.Sc/HND	60	65.2%
	MSc./MBA	18	19.6%
	Ph.D	7	7.6%
	Others	7	7.6%
	Total	92	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The years of experience indicates that the majority, 73.9% (68), have less than 5 years of experience, while 20.7% (19) have between 5 and 10 years. Only 5.4% (5) have more than 10 years of experience. This indicates that most respondents are relatively new in their professional roles, with a smaller proportion having long-term experience. Regarding the highest educational qualification, majority, 65.2% (60), hold a B.Sc./HND, while 19.6% (18) possess an M.Sc./MBA. Those with a Ph.D. account for 7.6% (7), and another 7.6% (7) fall under the “Others” category.

Table 2: Reliability Test of Research Constructs

Variables	No of items	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability Status
Integrity	5	0.812	Reliable
Professional competence	5	0.794	Reliable
Accountability	5	0.801	Reliable
Self-discipline	5	0.777	Reliable
Financial Reporting Quality	5	0.836	Reliable
Overall Scale	25	0.859	Reliable

Source: SPSS Output, 2026.

The table 2 presents the Cronbach’s Alpha values obtained for each construct and the overall scale. The results indicate that all variables surpassed the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.70 recommended for social science research (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Integrity recorded an alpha of 0.812, professional competence 0.794, accountability 0.801, self-discipline 0.777, and financial reporting quality 0.836. The overall scale produced an alpha value of 0.859. These results demonstrate that the instrument items were internally consistent and measured their respective constructs reliably.

Table 3: Regression Coefficients

Predictor	β Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Sig. (p-value)	Decision
Constant	0.524	0.186	2.816	0.006	-
INT	0.421	0.096	4.382	0.000	Significant
PC	0.387	0.098	3.952	0.001	Significant
ACC	0.359	0.099	3.624	0.002	Significant
SD	0.333	0.098	3.415	0.003	Significant

Source: SPSS Output, 2026

The table 3 reveals that all four predictors have positive and statistically significant effects on financial reporting quality at the 5% level. Integrity ($\beta = 0.421$, $p < 0.05$) had the strongest influence, followed by professional competence ($\beta = 0.387$, $p < 0.05$), accountability ($\beta = 0.359$, $p < 0.05$), and self-discipline ($\beta = 0.333$, $p < 0.05$). This implies that improvements in these ethical constructs significantly enhance the quality, reliability, and transparency of financial reporting in the University of Benin.

Hypothesis One

Integrity has no significant influence on the accuracy and reliability of financial reports in the University of Benin.

Since table 3 shows that integrity has a positive and statistically significant effect on financial reporting quality ($\beta = 0.421$, $p < 0.05$). This implies that higher levels of professional integrity among respondents enhance the accuracy and reliability of financial reports. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two

Professional competence has no significant effect on the transparency of financial reporting practices in the University of Benin.

The table 3 also indicates that professional competence significantly predicts transparency in financial reporting ($\beta = 0.387$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that when financial professionals

update and apply their knowledge, financial reports become more transparent. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Three

Accountability has no significant relationship with compliance to established accounting standards in the University of Benin.

The table 3 shows that accountability has a positive and significant effect on compliance with accounting standards ($\beta = 0.359$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that professionals who embrace accountability enhance compliance and trustworthiness in reporting. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Four

Self-discipline does not significantly contribute to the prevention of unethical manipulations in financial statements.

The table 3 reveals that self-discipline significantly reduces unethical practices in financial reporting ($\beta = 0.333$, $p < 0.05$). This means that professionals who adhere to deadlines, procedures, and ethical norms are less likely to manipulate financial data. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Table 4: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of Estimate
1	0.746	0.557	0.532	0.412

Source: SPSS Output, 2026.

The table 4 shows that the four predictors jointly explain 55.7% of the variation in financial reporting quality ($R^2 = 0.557$). The adjusted R^2 of 0.532 indicates a strong explanatory power, suggesting that personal ethics account for over half of the changes observed in financial reporting quality within the University of Benin.

Table 5: ANOVA Result

Model	Sum squares of	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	21.482	4	5.370	32.423	0.000
Residual	17.086	87	0.196		
Total	38.578	91			

Source: SPSS Output, 2026

The ANOVA results in Table 5 confirm that the regression model is statistically significant ($F(4,87) = 32.423$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that the predictors, integrity, professional competence, accountability, and self-discipline jointly have a significant effect on financial reporting quality.

4.2. Discussion

Integrity and Financial Reporting Quality

The results show that integrity had the strongest positive effect on financial reporting quality ($\beta = 0.421$, $p < 0.05$). This finding is consistent with the first objective of the study and aligns with prior works such as Beneish (1999). Similarly, Schaubroeck et al. (2012) found that integrity is a critical component of ethical leadership, generating trust and credibility inside organisations. Their research discovered that when integrity is continuously displayed, it inhibits unethical behaviour and enhances responsibility at all organisational levels. The implication for financial reporting is that technical conformity with accounting rules may not be sufficient to ensure dependability, whereas strong integrity protects reporting quality by incorporating honesty and transparency into professional procedures.

Professional Competence and Reporting Quality

Professional competence was also found to significantly influence transparency in financial reporting ($\beta = 0.387$, $p < 0.05$). Respondents strongly acknowledged the need for continuous learning and updating of knowledge, which resonates with Barth et al. (2008), who argue that competence improves disclosure quality. This underscores the importance

of ongoing professional development in ensuring that reports are not only accurate but also transparent and comparable.

Accountability and Reporting Quality

The analysis further revealed that accountability plays a significant role in enhancing compliance with established accounting standards ($\beta = 0.359, p < 0.05$). This aligns with Nelson (2003), who highlighted that accountability mechanisms help professionals maintain ethical behaviour even in discretionary reporting situations. The study participants overwhelmingly supported accountability as a means to strengthen trustworthiness and reduce the risk of misstatements.

Self-Discipline and Reporting Quality

Self-discipline also emerged as a significant predictor of financial reporting quality ($\beta = 0.333, p < 0.05$). Respondents indicated that self-discipline enables them to resist pressures, adhere to deadlines, and avoid conflicts of interest. This confirms the psychological frameworks of Murphy and Dacin (2011), which suggest that ethical resilience helps professionals counteract rationalizations for unethical practices.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1. Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the impact of personal ethics on the quality of financial reporting at the University of Benin. It looked specifically at how integrity, professional competence, accountability, and self-discipline influence financial reporting Quality The study's main finding is that integrity is the strongest predictor of reporting quality, implying that ethical standards of honesty and fairness are critical in ensuring correct financial information. Professional skill was also identified as a major predictor, showing the need of ongoing learning and expertise in improving transparency. Accountability was also acknowledged as a crucial motivator of conformity with established accounting standards, hence increasing trust and credibility in financial statements. Similarly, self-discipline helped to prevent unethical manoeuvres, allowing professionals to maintain ethical standards even while under duress.

4.2. Recommendations

In line with the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Strengthen Integrity Training: The University of Benin and professional bodies should institutionalise ethics workshops and seminars to reinforce integrity and honesty among financial professionals.
- ii. Continuous Professional Development: Accountants and auditors should engage in ongoing training to update their knowledge of evolving accounting standards and best practices, ensuring competence and transparency.
- iii. Enhance Accountability Mechanisms: Organisations should adopt monitoring systems, peer reviews, and transparent audit procedures that ensure accountability in financial reporting.
- iv. Promote Self-Discipline: Institutions should foster a culture that encourages self-regulation, adherence to deadlines, and resistance to external pressures to compromise financial integrity.

References

- Agyei-Mensah, B. K. (2017). The relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and IFRS 7 compliance: Evidence from market. *Corporate Governance*, 7(4), 486–503. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-06-2016-0129>
- Bailey, C. D., Scott, I., & Thoma, S. J. (2010). Revitalizing accounting ethics research in the neo-Kohlbergian framework: Putting the DIT into perspective. *Behavioural Research in Accounting*, 22(2), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.2308/bria.2010.22.2.1>
- Barth, M. E., Landsman, W. R., & Lang, M. H. (2008). International accounting standards and accounting quality. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 46(3), 467–498. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-679X.2008.00287.x>
- Beneish, M. D. (1999). The detection of earnings manipulation. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 55(5), 24–36. <https://doi.org/10.2469/faj.v55.n5.2296>
- Carter, S. L. (1996). *Integrity*. Harper Perennial.
- Dichev, I. D., Graham, J. R., Harvey, C. R., & Rajgopal, S. (2013). Earnings quality: Evidence from the field. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 56(2–3), 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2013.05.003>

- Duckworth, A. L., & Seligman, M. E. P. (2006). Self-discipline gives girls the edge: Gender in self-discipline, grades, and achievement test scores. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 98(1), 198–208. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.98.1.198>
- Epstein, R. M., & Hundert, E. M. (2002). Defining and assessing professional competence. *JAMA*, 287(2), 226–235.
- International Federation of Accountants. (2020). *Handbook of the International Code of Ethics for Professional Accountants*. International Ethics Standards Board for Accountants. <https://www.ifac.org/publications-resources/2020-handbook-international-code-ethics-professional-accountants>
- Kaplan, S. E. (2001). Ethically related judgments by observers of earnings management. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 32(4), 285–298. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010796829629>
- Kohlberg, L. (1981). *The philosophy of moral development*. Harper & Row.
- Murphy, P. R., & Dacin, M. T. (2011). Psychological pathways to fraud: Understanding and preventing fraud in organizations. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 101(4), 601–618. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-011-0741-0>
- Nelson, M. W. (2003). Behavioural evidence on the effects of principles- and rules-based standards. *Accounting Horizons*, 17(1), 91–104. <https://doi.org/10.2308/acch.2003.17.1.91>
- Okike, E. N. M. (2007). Corporate governance in Nigeria: The status quo. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 15(2), 173–193. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2007.00553.x>
- Osemeke, L., & Adegbite, E. (2016). Regulatory multiplicity and conflict: Towards a combined code on corporate governance in Nigeria. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 133(3), 431–451. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2405-3>
- Rest, J. R. (1986). *Moral development: Advances in research and theory*. Praeger.
- Schaubroeck, J. M., Hannah, S. T., Avolio, B. J., Kozlowski, S. W., Lord, R. G., Treviño, L. K., Dimotakis, N., & Peng, A. C. (2012). Embedding ethical leadership within and across organization levels. *Academy of Management Journal*, 55(5), 1053–1078. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2011.0064>

- Sinclair, A. (1995). The chameleon of accountability: Forms and discourses. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 20(2–3), 219–237. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682\(93\)E0003-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682(93)E0003-Y)
- Sweeney, B., & Costello, F. (2010). Moral intensity and ethical decision-making: An empirical examination of undergraduate accounting and business students. *Accounting Education: An International Journal*, 18(1), 75–97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639280802579658>
- Trevino, L. K. (1986). Ethical decision making in organizations: A person–situation interactionist model. *Academy of Management Review*, 11(3), 601–617.
- Wilson-Oshilim, U. D. & Efedhoma, P. E. (2024). Impact of artificial intelligence on financial reporting accuracy and efficiency. *Management Sciences Review*, 15(2), 1-18.